

Post-harvest Diseases of Mango their Management.

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Abstract

Mango is one of the major fruit crops of India. It is well known with name of King of Fruits. India contributes about 56 per cent of global production Botanical name of mango is *Mangifera indica* L. and is the most important species of the genus *Mangifera*. The main objective of this study was to find out the most important pre-harvest treatment and management of mango fruit to get the maximum fruit yield with better quality and shelf life of mango. Shelf life is one of the important quality characters for fruit production especially for climacteric fruits which might be affected by various factors. Post-harvest management means the handling of an agricultural product after harvest to prolong storage life, freshness and an attractive appearance. Postharvest diseases of mango include anthracnose, stem-end rot, Diplodia stem-end rot, black mould rot, brown spot and black spot rot. Rotting of fruits due to several other fungal infestation is also very common. Post-harvest diseases can be managed by preharvest spray with fungicides, careful handling during harvesting, sorting and grading, hot water treatment ($52\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, 10 minutes) and coating of fruits with essential oil/s help in management of post-harvest diseases of mango. There is a need to focus on use of nontoxic substances, biocontrol control and physical methods to manage post-harvest diseases.

Keyword

Mango, Postharvest disease, Rot, Grading and Fungicide.

Introduction

Mango is native of india and one of the major fruit crops of India. It is well known with name of King of Fruits. The Mango is the national fruit of India, Pakistan, Philippines and Bangladesh. India contributes about 56 per cent of global production. Botanical name of mango is *Mangifera indica* L. and is the most important species of the genus *Mangifera*, which produces the most delicious fruit called the mango. It belongs to the dicotyledonous family Anacardiaceae. The genus *Mangifera* contains about 49 species, of which 8 are of doubtful status and 41 are valid species. Morphologically the genus could be separated under two sections based on the character of the flower disc: the first, with 34 species, has flowers with well-developed swollen disc, and the second, with 7 species, has obsolete or pedicellate disc. Mango is grown in all tropical countries. Mango fruits are greatly relished for their succulence, pleasant flavour and delicious taste. They are also a rich source of Beta-carotene, the precursor of vitamin-A, which is essential for the prevention of night blindness in human beings and rich source of vitamin-C also. Many parts of the plant, namely, trunk, branch, twig, leaf, petiole, flower and fruit have many pharmacological properties like Anticancer, Antidiabetic, Anti-inflammatory, Hepatoprotective, Anti-hemorrhagic, Anti-tetanus, Analgesic and Antipyretic, Kidney damage, Anti-ulcer, Antibacterial, Antifungal, Antiviral, Antimalarial etc. In India, mango is one of the sacred fruits and finds place on religious ceremonies. It is grown in almost all the parts of our country India and is the most important fruit crop.

Although mango is affected by large number of diseases but some diseases are of great economic importance and are responsible for high loss in the mango production in our country. The mango crop is affected by large number of diseases but some diseases are of great economic importance and are responsible for high loss in the mango production in our country. It is very essential to protect the fruits from post-harvest diseases as the post-harvest losses are huge. More than 25% mangoes are spoiled in India because of lack of proper postharvest management technique. To reduce the postharvest losses, it is essential to start protecting it in the field and then careful harvesting, hygienic handling, packaging and storage, temperature regulated transportation and finally intelligent marketing. Mango fruits are susceptible to many postharvest diseases mainly caused by fungi and bacteria. Injury during harvesting, defective handling, high temperature and high relative humidity during harvest and storage affect the storage life of the fruits. Presence of blemished fruits along with healthy ones also contributes to the fruit decay. If there is any surface bruise or injury on the fruit, micro-organisms such as fungi and bacteria invade into it and cause internal decay. High temperature and high relative humidity accelerate process of postharvest decaying by microorganisms. Some important post-harvest diseases of mango are Anthracnose (caused by *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*), Stem end rot (*Lasiodyplodia theobromae*), Black Rot (*Aspergillus niger*), Botryosphaeria rot (*Botryosphaeria ribis*), Stem end soft rot (*Ceratocystis paradoxa*), rot (*Pestalotiopsis versicolor*), Phoma rot (*Phoma mangiferae*),

Alternaria rot (*Alternaria tenuissima*), Rhizopus rot (*Rhizopus arrhizus*), Grey mould (*Botrytis cinerea*) etc. The main objective of the experimental study was to find out the most important pre-harvest treatment to get the maximum fruit yield with better quality and shelf life of mango.

Diseases and their management

1. **Anthracoze** (*Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*)
Symptoms: Leaves, stems, young flowers and fruit are affected. Sunken black spots appear on the surface of the fruit during ripening. Disease gradually spreads and whole fruit get rotten and also spreads to other fruits in the lot. High relative humidity, high temperature, fruit injuries during harvest are the predisposing factors. Inoculum remains on dried leaves, defoliated branches, mummified flowers and flower brackets. Spread through air-borne conidia

Management: Spray with mancozeb (2.0 g/L) or prochloraz (2 g/L) or Copper oxychloride sprays (4 g/L) weekly during flowering and then monthly until harvest. Harvested fruits should be treated with carbendazim (0.5g/L) before storage. Dip fruits within 24 hours of harvest for 5 minutes in hot water (52°C). Benomyl was found more effective against quiescent infections of anthracnose of mango in hot water than cold water. The effectiveness of hot water dips as post-harvest treatments for the control of mango anthracnose has been known for many years. Dip treatment .

2. **Stem End Rot** (*Lasiodiplodia theobromae*)
Symptoms In fruits, the pericarp base of the pedicel become black Later, it enlarges to form a circular, black patch and which further extends rapidly and whole fruit become completely black within two or three days., The pulp becomes brown and softer.

Management : Avoid harvesting of immature fruits. Dip fruits within 24 hours of harvest for 5 minutes in hot water (52°C). Post-harvest treatment with carbendazim (0.5g/L). Controlled atmosphere storage i.e. cold storage. Fruit from orchards with stem end rot infection should be rejected for long term storage.

3. **Black mould rot:** (*Aspergillus niger*) Symptoms Yellowing of base of fruit and development of irregular, hazy, greyish spots. Mesocarp of the rotted (soft rot) area of fruit become depressed. The fruit surface covered blackish fungal growth.

Management: Careful handling of fruits at all stages to avoid mechanical injury and sap bum damage to the fruits. Pre-harvest sprays and post-harvest dip of fruit in hot water containing carbendazim (0.05%) for 5m at 52± 1 0C to prevent fungus already seated in the injuries. Storing fruits at 12°C prevents the rotting.

4. **Botryosphaeria rot** (*Botryosphaeria ribis*)
Symptoms The first sign is a slight softening of the tissue around the spot. The affected skin turns

brown and the flesh beneath become black. Lesions on the fruits are dark, sunken and oval to round, sometimes elliptical with a shallow decay of the flesh beneath. Minute black bodies are formed in the skin and white to grey mouldy growth is developed. Various symptoms viz., purplish brown spots and stem end rot have been noticed on mango fruits with a decay of flesh beneath.

Management: Strict orchard hygiene and good tree vigour should be maintained. Pre-harvest spraying of fungicide viz., carbendazim (0.05-0.1 %). Dipping of fruits in hot water (52± 10C for 30m) after harvest. Harvesting of fruits with stalk.

5. **Phoma rot** (*Phoma mangiferae*) Symptoms Black to brown spots are present on the entire fruit surface. Outer skin is hard but the internal portion rot quickly. In advance stage, dark pycnidia appear over such rotten tissues. Pycnidia are irregular in shape and liberate small rounded spores when pressed.

Management: Maintenance of field hygiene. Removal of diseased fruits helpsto limit the disease spread before sclerotia can proliferate and fall on to the soil. Careful handling of harvested fruits to avoid soil contamination and bruising. Fruits, which may have field infection, can be treated by means of a post-harvest fungicide dip.

6. **Alternaria rot** (*Alternaria tenuissima*) Symptoms: On fruits, initially the spots are water soaked and later become black, circular and sub-cuticular. Spots gradually enlarge and become irregular. Initially the decay is firm and does not penetrate into the pulp. Later, the disease makes headway into the flesh. The centre of the spots is slightly sunken. Under humid conditions dark brown spores are seen over the lesions. In advance stages, the whole fruit becomes rotten. When the skin of diseased fruit is removed, reddish patches can be seen on the flesh below the lesions.

Management: Field sanitation. Sprays with protectant fungicide mancozeb (0.2%) at 15 days interval until fruit set. Post-harvest dip with thiophanate methyle or prochloraz (0.1%). Fruits should be stored at lower temperature (10-120C).

7. **Rhizopus rot** (*Rhizopus arrhizus*) Symptoms: Fungus enters the fruit through injuries and becomes more destructive at higher temperature. The disease is characterized by large watersoaked areas developing on any portion of the fruit with profuse growth of the fungus with black sporangial bodies. Skin is easily displaced from infected flesh. Emitting foul smell. Liquid leak from the fruit and the odour is peculiar and unpleasant. There is profuse development of coarse white mould strands giving rise to globular white spore heads (sporangia), which later turn black and easily visible to naked eyes. Sporangia arise from dark branched, rootlike structure (rhizoids).

Management: Strict hygiene in orchard should be maintained. Pre-harvest spray with mancozeb (2g/L) help to reduce post-harvest rotting. Fallen and rejected fruits should be removed and destroyed. Care should be taken during harvesting and handling of the fruits. Post-harvest dip in thiophanate methyl (0.1 %) Heat treatment ($52\pm 1^{\circ}$ C for 30m) is essential to deactivate latent infection. Fruit should be stored at lower temperature (10-12°C).

Conclusion

This study has been carried out to investigate the post-harvest disease of mango fruits, pre-harvest and post-harvest management of post-harvest disease and the efficiencies of different control measures. The economic costs of such postharvest losses are higher than the field losses. The successful management of such diseases depends on understanding the biology of the pathogen, that promote disease development and the economics, efficacy and market acceptability of the various control measures.

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